

APPLICATION OF COMPLEX NUMBERS IN PROBLEMS OF GEOMETRY

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To succeed in mathematics you need a wide array of tools to have a chance of finding one for the problems you encounter. Here we discuss one tool often overlooked in competitive mathematics, the usage of complex numbers to solve geometry problems. Infamous for creating long and unintuitive solutions, complex solutions are often avoided in favour of synthetic solutions but given the right circumstances a complex solution might actually be the best option. Theoretically, all geometry problems can be solved using complex numbers. However, the practicality differs immensely. Sometimes it will just be too messy. Complex numbers can be written using different forms.

Rectangular form: Written on the form $z = a + bi$

Polar form: Written on the form $z = r(\cos \theta + i \sin \theta)$

Exponential form: Written on the form $z = re^{i\theta}$

r is the distance to the point from the origin. θ is the angle the complex number (as a vector) makes with the real axis. Positive angles go counterclockwise and negative angles clockwise. The angle, when speaking of complex numbers, is called the argument.

Angles

A frequent application for complex numbers is determining the angle between two lines. The easiest example of this is if you have two complex numbers and you represent both using two vectors. In order to calculate the angle between

these two vectors you take the quotient of the numbers. When multiplying two complex numbers you add their arguments. Similarly, when you divide, you subtract the arguments and this difference will be the angle between the lines.

$$z_1 z_2 = r_1 e^{i\theta_1} r_2 e^{i\theta_2} = r_1 r_2 e^{i(\theta_1 + \theta_2)}$$

Most of the time you will not have a single number which is representative of a line, but rather two numbers which lay on the line, say a and b . The direction of the line will be the equivalent of a vector going from a to b . This vector can be written as $b - a$.

If you have two lines and want to find the angle between them, you may take the quotient. However, if you do not have any actual numbers, then you cannot interpret your answer. This is solved by using a property of conjugate

numbers. If your quotient is real, then your answer will be its own conjugate. Take two lines and let a and b lie on line 1 and c and d on line 2. If the two lines are parallel then the following relationship will be true.

If two lines are perpendicular to each other then it means that their quotient would be a purely imaginary number. The complex conjugate of an imaginary number is the original number with an inverted sign.

There is another useful relation which can be derived from the relationship regarding parallel lines and collinearity. Take three points a , b and c . If a vector going from a to b is parallel to a vector going from a to c then they are collinear.

Circles

Circles often pose a problem for solutions involving complex numbers as most ways of expressing them quickly become unwieldy in more difficult problems. There is however one exception. At the heart of almost every complex solution lies the unit circle. By identifying a prominent circle in the problem statement and letting that circle be the unit circle the solution can be massively simplified using the following properties.

These properties, unique to the unit circle, makes many problems trivial that would otherwise be infeasible. Complex solutions are therefore best reserved for problems containing no more than one predominant circle. As long as that is true they can produce short and simple proofs. Consider for example a complex proof of the inscribed angle theorem.

Triangles

Equipped to deal with angles and circles the only thing that remains is triangles. Solving geometry problems without a way of expressing triangle centers would be a daunting task. Luckily they can often be expressed using simple expressions.

Perhaps the simplest triangle center to express using complex numbers is the centroid, the point within the triangle where the three medians meet. For a given triangle ABC the centroid can be expressed as $\frac{a+b+c}{3}$. Expressing the incenter and circumcenter (the center of the inscribed circle and circumscribed circle respectively) in the general case is not as simple. This can however easily be solved by letting the incircle or circumcircle be the unit circle. In the former case it is then often beneficial to express every point in

terms of the tangent points instead of the triangle corners. By doing this the incenter or circumcenter simply becomes 0.

Lastly, the orthocenter (the point where the altitudes of a triangle meet) also benefits from having its triangle corners lie on the unit circle. As long as this is the case the orthocenter of a triangle ABC can also be expressed in a simple expression as $a + b + c$.

Transformations

In geometry it is important to be able to manipulate figures and points freely. When using complex numbers this becomes easy thanks to a few relations. Translation is easy, it is the same as with cartesian coordinates. You simply add or subtract the number that represents the desired translation. Reflections and rotations are not that difficult either. The reflection of point z through the origin is, like with cartesian coordinates, $-z$. This is frequently used when a point lies on the unit circle. The reflection of point z_1 through point z_2 will therefore result in $2z_2 - z_1$. Intuitively, it could be seen as taking the vector difference $z_2 - z_1$ and adding z_2 . Alternatively, it could be seen as translating the coordinate system so that z_2 gets translated onto 0, reflecting z_1 through 0, and translating back.

If you wish to rotate a point a certain amount of radians around another point, using cartesian coordinates will be very difficult, but with complex numbers this is very easy. Suppose you wish to rotate a point A ϕ radians counterclockwise around another point B . To do this you create the complex number

representing the vector from B to A , which is $a - b$. Then this vector is rotated by multiplying it with $e^{i\phi}$. The following number is your rotated vector starting at the origin. In order to have your rotated vector start from B , you simply add b to the vector.

$$c = (a - b)e^{i\phi} + b$$

More frequently written as

$$c - b = (a - b)e^{i\phi}$$

If ϕ is negative, it will instead rotate clockwise.

Theorem. *The rotation of A around B ϕ radians onto C have the relation*
 $c - b = (a - b)e^{i\phi}$

Practice problems

Problem 1. Prove that the midpoints of the altitudes of the triangle are collinear if and only if the triangle is rectangular.

Problem 2. Let H_1 and H_2 be feet of perpendiculars from the orthocenter H of the triangle ABC to the bisectors of external and internal angles at the vertex C . Prove that the line H_1H_2 contains the midpoint of the side AB .

Problem 3. (IMO 1998 shortlist) Let ABC be a triangle such that $\angle ACB = 2 \angle ABC$. Let D be the point of the segment BC such that $CD = 2BD$. The segment AD is extended over the point D to the point E for which $AD = DE$. Prove that: $\angle ECB + 180^\circ = 2 \angle EBC$.

Conclusion

We hope that we have given you some insight into the application of complex numbers in geometric problem solving. If you already knew of the concept but disregarded it as an unviable method we hope to have freed you from this misconception.

Used sources:

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